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TECHNOLOGYFARMING OF WHITE GUM TREE : *SENEGALIA SENEGAL* (L.) WILLD. IN THE
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ABSTRACT

This study on the use of white gum by farmers was carried out in Mandalia and the surrounding area. Its aim was to determine the perceptions and socio-economic uses of *Senegalia senegal* stands. Participatory surveys were carried out on the different types of use and management of *Senegalia senegal* in agrosystems. A total of 110 men and women were interviewed. The exploitation of *S. senegal* is essentially based on the production of gum arabic, firewood and fodder. *S. senegal* is also used in agrosystems for soil fertilisation, shading and stocking (living hedges). Use of *S. senegal* varies according to gender and needs. 71.42% of men and 28.5% of women harvest this species for the production of gum arabic (90%), firewood (60%), fodder (80%), soil fertility (60%) and living hedges (60%). The survival rate of underground shoots at weaning was very low (25%). This means that the survival of weaned offspring depends on a number of factors. In addition to its economic interest, it is currently the species used in the fight against desertification in the Sahel. In the interests of future generations, this species must be taken into account in programmes for the conservation and sustainable development of plant genetic resources of socio-economic interest.

Keywords: *Senegalia senegal*, exploitation, gum arabic, Mandalia, Chad.

1. INTRODUCTION

Non-timber forest products play an important role in improving the living conditions of people in rural areas where poverty is rife with an incidence of around 40.1% (INSD, 2015). These Non-timber forest products include gum arabic, which is produced mainly in the Sahel region of Burkina Faso. It is a natural exudate harvested from the trunk and branches of trees in the *Acacia* family (Daniele *et al.*, 2011). The decline in food production over the last two decades, combined with population and livestock growth, has led to strong pressure on forest resources. This high pressure has led to a significant change in the structure of the vegetation, resulting in the loss of species with high medicinal, food and artisanal value (Dougnon *et al.*, 2016 ; Fundiko *et al.*, 2017 ; Sina *et al.*, 2019). In Chad, traditional gum harvesting is based on anarchic collection, and no forecasts can be made from one year to the next due to the lack of a control structure capable of guiding the efforts of producer farmers to increase their production, and encouraging the constitution of buffer stocks capable of making up for the shortfall in merchandise between seasons (Hamel, 1988 ; FAO, 2000). The gum trees exploited in Chad, in particular *S. senegal* and *Vachellia seyal*, form more or less extensive stands of varying density, in a mixture or in a pure state (Mbayngone *et al.*, 2017). At five years of age, a gum tree can be bled and will produce gum as regularly as the climate will allow for a dozen years (Giffard, 1975). Chad has only recently become aware of the importance of this product to its national trade (FAO, 2000). The first exports only date from 1956-1957, with less than 60 tonnes controlled (Giffard, 1975). Current production is estimated at 12,000 tonnes (Jamin and Seiny Boukar, 2002). In Chad, *Senegalia senegal* is found mainly in the Ouaddaï, Biltine, Batha, Salamat and Guéra regions (OSS, 2015 ; Ngaryo *et al.* 2015 ; Mbayngone *et al.*, 2017). Drought years have led to a southward shift in its range, particularly in Chari-Baguirmi, Lac and Kanem (OSS, 2015 ; Mbayngone *et al.*, 2017). The droughts of the 1970s led to the dieback of gum tree stands, a decline in gum production, the weakening of the commercial structures established for this purpose, and the abandonment of some demobilised

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producers in the face of private economic operators who were more voracious than ever (Carette and Gaverns, 1999). Since 1985, there has been a revival, a revival of economic interest and a certain speculation in gum production (FAO, 2000). This has led to land conflicts between natives and immigrants in certain favoured areas. Few studies have specifically assessed the ethnobotanical knowledge of the local population on the use of *S. senegal* in Chad. The main objective of this study is to compile an inventory of the uses made of *S. senegal*. The specific objectives are (i) to evaluate the forms of use and management methods of *S. senegal* plantations in Chad, and (ii) to discuss the agroforestry role of *S. senegal*.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study site

The investigations were carried out in the Department of Mandalia, located approximately 50km south-east of N'Djamena (Chari-Baguirmi), between latitudes 11° 25' - 11° 52' North and longitudes 15° 00' - 15° 25' East. The climate is characterised by two contrasting seasons (a dry season from November to May and a rainy season from June to October). According to Aubreville (1950), this kind of rainfall is typical of the Sudano-Sahelian environment, with isohyets ranging from 400 to 700mm. The average annual temperature is around 35°C, with variations between 10 and 45°C. The soil is clayey or sandy, with occasional vertisols. In exundated areas, there are two types of soil: hydromorphic soil-vertisol complex and hydromorphic soil-holomorphic soil complex (Cabot, 1973). The vegetation has three main physiognomic types, often closely intermingled (OSS, 2015) :

- the steppe type, which is most common on arid sites for climatic or edaphic reasons ;

- the savannah type, which occupies most of the "average" sites for the same reasons, where plant species such as *Ziziphus mauritiana*, *Mitragyna inermis*, *Senegalia senegal*, *Vachellia nilotica*, *V. seyal* and *Bauhinia rufescens* thrive ;

- the "prairie" type, always hydromorphic, which can be assigned to one or other of the 2 previous types depending on whether the grass cover consists mainly of annual or perennial grasses such as *Eragrotis avirensis*, *Sporobolus* sp...

Depending on the topography, the following dominant species can be found : *Hyphaene thebaica*, *Anogeissus leiocarpus*, *Balanites aegyptiaca*, *Ficus microcarpa*, *Combretum glutinosum*, *Guiera senegalensis*, *Vachellia sieberiana*, *Tamarindus indica* and *Sclerocarya birrea*, found on sandy to sandy-loam soils in exposed areas. These trees make up the plant formations corresponding to tree savannas (OSS, 2015).

Figure 1 : Map of the study area

3. MONOGRAPHIC STUDY OF *SENEGALIA SENEGAL*

A deciduous shrub 2 to 6 m high and, rarely, a tree, up to 8 m, *Senegalia senegal* is spiny and sarmentose when young (Arbonnier, 2019). It belongs to the Fabaceae superfamily and the Rosales order (Joke, 2000). Like most Acacias, it develops according to the Troll architectural model (Muthana, 1988). An orthotropic trunk is acquired by straightening the plagiotropic axes in an oblique plane (Vassal, 1998). The crown is a ball or a parasol. Twigs with monopodial growth have alternate spiral phyllotaxis and lateral sexuality (Muller, 2004 ; Bâ, 2008 ; Fagg & Allison, 2004). The biparipinnate leaves have 3 to 8 pairs of pinnules. Each pinnule bears 7 to 25 pairs of leaflets (Photo 2). At the base of the petiole are 3 stipules transformed into blackish spines that are grouped together and curved in the shape of hooks. The medial spine is turned towards the base of the branch, while the other two diverge laterally. The inflorescence is spike-like. According to Diallo (1994), their white to yellow flowers (3 to 12 cm) are all sessile and complete hermaphrodites. The yellow to brown fruit is a dehiscent, oblong, flat pod 2 to 19 cm long. It contains 3 to 6 flattened, reticulated seeds. Assoumane (2011) distinguishes five varieties, one of which has not been described. These are : var. *senegal*, var. *rostrata*, var. *kerensis*, var. *leiorhachis*. These different varieties are each characterised by the floral axis, which may be glabrous or sub-glabrous (var. *leiorhachis* and var. *senegal*), and densely or sparsely pubescent (var. *kerensis* and var. *rostrata*).

Photo 1 : Young *Senegalia senegal* plant (A) and *Senegalia senegal* gum arabic (B)

4. SAMPLING AND DATA COLLECTION

Surveys of farmers

The ethnobotanical study of *Senegalia senegal* was carried out among the people of Mandalia and the surrounding villages. The study was conducted using the active participatory research and planning method (M.A.R.P). A checklist of questionnaires was prepared for the interviews. These semi-structured interviews (S.S.I.) consisted of closed and open questions. The interviewees (105 in total) were women, men, young and old. Most spoke local Arabic. Information was collected on *S. senegal* farming in general. Three stratification criteria were used to select the study area, namely the density of the farming population, floristic diversity and market frequentation. After the interviews, a field visit was made with a number of farmers who were willing to accompany us into the field to show us the different gum arabic harvesting techniques and agroforestry practices. We were also given the vernacular names of local plants.

Statistical analysis

The ethnobotanical data was analysed by calculating response frequencies. For a given parameter, the frequency of responses is determined by the quotient, expressed as a percentage, of the number of people who gave the answer by the total number of respondents. An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to check whether the number of uses cited by the respondents varied according to their category of farm.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-demographic characteristics of the farmers

Of the farmers interviewed, 71.42% were men and 28.58% women. According to the FAO (2002), women in Chad use *S. senegal* as a source of wood and food. Men mainly harvest gum arabic, which is sold on the market. Most farmers are young, with 54.28% aged between 10 and 30, while the elderly (over 50) account for only 5.7% of farmers. Around 40% of extractors are aged between 30 and 50. This can be explained by the fact that tapping operations require a lot of energy. The level of education of the operators varies : 31.42% are illiterate, 28.57% have primary education, 31.42% have secondary education and 8.57% have higher education. For some farmers, extracting *S. senegal* gum is a secondary activity to increase their income. For schoolchildren, it is an extracurricular activity that provides them with some income.

Characteristics of *Senegalia senegal* farms

Senegalia senegal is found in Acacia parks, fields, or preserved in more or less isolated form in agrosystems and sometimes in a spontaneous state in wooded areas. In agrosystems where *S. senegal* is present, the size of holdings varies from 1ha to 24ha. Generally, this species is planted by seedlings, since we identified a total of almost 45.42% planted trees and 54.58% from natural regeneration, particularly natural seedlings. In the agrosystems, the density is around 11 trees/hectare. This density is very low compared with that of Kordofan (Sudan), where some agrosystems have more than 50 trees per hectare (Depierre, 1969).

Importance of woody species

For the livestock farmers interviewed, *Senegalia senegal* is a plant with a high fodder value that is appreciated by livestock. This confirms the observations of Ickowicz *et al* (2005) on the fodder importance of this species. On the other hand, *Faidherbia albida*, *Vachellia polyacantha* and *Bauhinia rufescens* are cited as agroforestry plants involved in improving degraded soils (Table 2). *Borassus aethiopum*, *Calotropis procera* and *Piliostigma reticulatum*, species that are generally found in fields left fallow, have a major drawback according to farmers, as they are known to invade uncontrollably and require a great deal of work to prepare the soil for cultivation. The wood of certain species such as *Tamarindus indica*, *Celtis integrifolia* and *S. senegal* is much in demand in the manufacture of numerous objects such as mortars, pestles, benches and frameworks. The local species encountered play an important role in daily survival and in restoring the ecological balance. They provide food, medicines, timber, firewood and fodder for livestock. Certain species with high agroforestry potential protect and improve agricultural crops, helping to improve the quality of life in the village. They provide work and income, and protection against wind, erosion and sun. Most of these species are preserved in agrosystems or wooded areas because they are used by farmers (FAO, 2000). According to the FAO (2000), Chad's main non-timber forest products are gum arabic, shea nuts and dates. In our study area, the date palm, *Phoenix dactylifera* (Arecaceae) and the shea nut, *Vitellaria paradoxa* (Sapotaceae) are absent. The populations are mainly focused on the exploitation of gum arabic.

Table 2 : Main woody species used and protected by local communities

Species	Family	Vernacular name (local Arabic)	Priority uses
<i>Vachellia laeta</i>	Fabaceae	Kitir azarak	Gum, wood
<i>Vachellia nilotica</i>	Fabaceae	Garat	Tannin, rope, forage
<i>Vachellia seyal</i>	Fabaceae	kouke	Gum, forage, wood
<i>Adansonia digitata</i>	Bombacaceae	Calacouca	Fruit, shade
<i>Balanites aegyptiaca</i>	Balanitaceae	Idjilite	Fruit, leaves, wood
<i>Bauhinia rufescens</i>	Fabaceae	Coulcoule	Forage, wood
<i>Bombax costatum</i>	Malvaceae		Fibre, food, wood
<i>Borassus aethiopica</i>	Aracaceae	Delep	Fruit, wood, carpentry
<i>Calotropis procera</i>	Asclepiadaceae	Achoro	Wood, fibre

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<i>Celtis integrifolia</i>	Ulmaceae	Ahla	Shade, wood
<i>Combretum glutinosum</i>	Combretaceae		Forage, wood
<i>Diospyros mespiliformis</i>	Ebenaceae	Durcane	Fruit, forage, shade
<i>Faidherbia albida</i>	Fabaceae	Haraze	Fruit, wood
<i>Ficus sicomauris</i>	Moraceae	Djimes	Fruit, shade, wood
<i>Hyphaene thebaica</i>	Arecaceae	Dome	Fruit, wood
<i>Khaya senegalensis</i>	Meliaceae	Mouraye	Forage, timber
<i>Mitragyna inermis</i>	Rubiaceae	Hinné	Shade, wood, forage
<i>Piliostigma reticulatum</i>	Fabaceae	Haroum	Forage, wood
<i>Tamarindus indica</i>	Fabaceae	Ardep	Fruit, shade
<i>Ziziphus mauritiana</i>	Ramnaceae	Nabak	Fruit, wood

The importance of species in ecosystem management and sustainable natural resource management

As Bellefontaine et al (2005) point out, in tropical zones with a prolonged dry season, knowledge of the regeneration processes of woody species is still very limited, and this is a handicap when it comes to implementing sustainable management of natural resources. The aim of sustainable management of natural resources (fuelwood, fodder, medicines, effects on erosion) is to ensure their long-term survival and to increase the density of fragile ecosystems, while meeting the needs of current and future populations. Revegetation by suckering and, if necessary, rejection is an inexpensive strategy that allows the area to be colonised. In our study area, species such as *Vachellia nilotica*, *V. seyal*, *Adansonia digitata*, *Anogeissus leocarpa*, *Bauhinia rufescens*, *Bombax costatum*, *Combretum glutinosum*, *Diospyros mespiliformis*, *Faidherbia albida*, *Guiera senegalensis*, *Hyphaene thebaica*, *Khaya senegalensis*, *Mitragyna inermis*, *Piliostigma reticulatum*, *Tamarindus indica* and *Ziziphus mauritiana* are suckering species (Bellefontaine et al. , 2005; Kosma, 2005). This ability can be used to propagate these species at low cost. *Acacia senegal*, on the other hand, does not suckle but forms underground shoots or adventitious shoots. Controlling the suckering process can help to rejuvenate stands. If, by cutting the species, the farmers protect the offshoots, they are acting in the interests of sustainable natural resource management. For the farmers, by protecting the offshoots, the latter can be bled and will produce gum arabic as much as possible. Today, certain species with a high socio-economic value, such as *S. senegal*, *Acacia laeta*, *Balanites aethiopica* and *Tamarindus indica*, are much used by local populations and are therefore destroyed in an uncontrolled manner. The survival of young shoots, especially underground shoots, appears to be the main factor on which efforts should be focused for the management of these ecosystems.

Endogenous use of *Senegalia senegal*

Senegalia senegal is used by traders, farmers, nomadic herders, schoolchildren, students and civil servants. The high percentages of favourable responses (Table 2) attest to the importance of this species to the local population. Most people use this species to produce gum arabic, the main commercial product (Photo 2). It is used for food, pharmacopoeia and handicrafts. Livestock farmers use it both as fodder and as firewood, as the leaves, pods and fruit are available during critical periods for Sahelian livestock farming. It is also used as firewood and fuel, especially by women (FAO, 2002 ; Abdou et al., 2013 ; Sina et al., 2019). The trunk and branches are used to make tool handles, roof supports and hut frames. A decoction is made from the bark to treat stomach ailments.

Photo 2: Gum Arabic from *S. senegal* (A) and *V. seyal* (B) sold on the market

Table 2: Frequency with which different uses of *S. senegal* are cited

Type of use	Citation frequency (%)
Supply	90,6%
Improving soil fertilisation	53,11%
Forage	82,75%
Shading	50,35%
Pharmacopoeia	47,41%
Fuel wood	70,85%
Timber	30,41%
Living hedge	50,16%

Agroforestry role of *Senegalia senegal* in the fight against *Striga hermonthica*

In addition to its role in producing gum arabic, *Senegalia senegal* plays a significant agroecological role. It protects, improves and fertilises the soil, and also provides shade. For some farmers, *Senegalia senegal* is very pungent and difficult to manage in the field. Farmers note that leaf litter improves soil fertility. On small farms, it is planted on the edges of agrosystems. 40% of the farmers interviewed noted the presence of *Striga hermonthica* on their farms. The presence of this phanerogam depends on the density of *Acacia* present in the agrosystems. In agrosystems with a high density of *S. senegal* (>30 plants/ha) this phanerogam is rare, sometimes absent. 51.42% of farmers surveyed adopted the method of manual uprooting and fertilisation to control *Striga hermonthica*. Fallowing was adopted by 20% of farmers and manual uprooting without fertilisation by 28.57%.

6. CONCLUSION

The way *Senegalia senegal* is used varies from one group of farmers to another. In general, they are the production of gum arabic, fodder, protection, improvement and fertilisation of the soil. From all the above we can say that *S. senegal* is a tree of great utility to local populations. However, over-exploitation has a negative influence on the structure of future population. The survival of the species is thus compromised under heavy human pressure. Urbanisation and excessive exploitation are among the causes of the reduction in *S. senegal* populations. The sustainable management of ecosystems, the diversification of sources of income and the creation of a NTFP sector with high value-added potential require the validation of ethnobotanical knowledge.

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Given the ever-increasing importance of the species (food, therapeutic, economic, etc.), promoting its conservation through the rational use of its various parts is becoming a priority action in the overall strategy for the conservation of plant genetic resources. Investigations must continue in order to confirm the capacity for regeneration.

7. CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest between the authors of this article.

8. AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTION

OD carried out the field work, performed the statistical analysis and drafted the manuscript. OD and NC designed the research project, gave the practical advices SP and MY contributed in statistical analysis. NC supervised the work and improved the manuscript. All the authors read, revised and approved the final manuscript.

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